

Machiavelli in the classroom: circulation and transfer of knowledge between Europe and the Americas

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ABSTRACT: The article studies the reception and interpretation of Machiavelli in Spain and Hispanic America between 1914 and 1950, focusing on considerations regarding the thoughts of the Florentine author expressed by prominent Argentine and Spanish professors of Political Law and Philosophy of Law, among them: Mariano de Vedia y Mitre, Faustino Legón, Tomás Casares, Adolfo Posada, Luis Legaz y Lacambra and Francisco Javier Conde. Through this analysis, the article addresses two problems: the academic and university reception of Machiavelli, and the characteristics of liberal and illiberal political thought during the selected period.

KEYWORDS: Political thought; Political law; Political theory; Authoritarianism; Republicanism; Liberalism.

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RESUMEN: El artículo estudia la recepción y la interpretación de Maquiavelo en el mundo atlántico de habla hispana (España e Hispanoamérica) entre 1914 y 1950, focalizándose en las consideraciones que desplegaron acerca del pensamiento del autor florentino destacados profesores argentinos y españoles de Derecho Político y de Filosofía del Derecho, entre ellos: Mariano de Vedia y Mitre, Faustino Legón, Tomás Casares, Adolfo Posada, Luis Legaz y Lacambra y Francisco Javier Conde. A través de este análisis, el artículo aborda dos problemas: la recepción académica y universitaria de Maquiavelo, y las características del pensamiento político liberal y antiliberal durante el período seleccionado.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Pensamiento político; Derecho político; Teoría política; Autoritarismo; Republicanismo; Liberalismo.

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INTRODUCTION

Niccolo Machiavelli (1469-1527) is a central author in the history of Western political thought. This is demonstrated by the sustained interest that his texts (especially *The Prince* and the *Discorsi*) have aroused since the 16th century and the controversy that has surrounded them. The Florentine has been associated with political principles that are not only different but diametrically opposed to each other (principality and republic, tyranny, and freedom), and his very name came to define abject and deplorable behaviors (treason, lying, unscrupulousness in a broad sense, violence, and even murder).

Indeed, several of the central authors of the Western canon of political thought (Aristotle, Hobbes, Rousseau, to mention three exemplary cases) have been the subject of controversy, read through different ideological prisms, and invoked to support dissimilar experiences, political phenomena and forms of government (although there are others who are less controversially linked to specific political trends, as is the case of Locke with liberalism). However, in the case of Machiavelli, if, certainly, there have been interpretations and reading traditions that have linked him to authoritarianism, and others to freedom, his is a singular case, even in comparison with other classical authors, for the debates around his ideas and his legacy have transcended intellectual or scholarly polemics, generating repudiation and censorship, and inciting, as has been illustratively pointed out, scandal and horror (Strauss, 1964; Berlin, 1992).

In addition, Machiavelli enjoys significant topicality in philosophy and political theory. Contemporary academic production has established a new consensus, according to which the author of the *Discorsi* is no longer synonymous with perversity, tyranny, arbitrariness, state reason, or any other phenomenon of politics, but is a reference for freedom, the republic, and even democratic radicalism; an author closer to the people than to the powerful. In this new consensus, historiography has played an important role, since, in the mid-1970s, authors such as John Pocock (1975) and above all Quentin Skinner (1984) portrayed Machiavelli as a republican and champion of freedom.

However, this new “canon” or consensus on Machiavelli has reached a certain saturation point. In fact, in recent times, objections and challenges have multiplied, to the point of proposing the need to return to the texts, or to recover important themes in his work that have been overlooked, precisely because of the recurrence of making the Florentine a theorist of political radicalism. From these points of view, the current prevailing academic production on Machiavelli would be one more chapter of the phenomenon discussed above, an ideological reappropriation of questionable academic and textual solvency (Zuckert, 2019; Portinaro, 2021; Landi, 2022).

However, it must be said that there is still a sizeable vacuum about the reception of Machiavelli and the traditions of reading and exegesis of his writings. This refers to Spanish-speaking countries. The most important production on the subject is confined to the political and

theological reflection of the Spanish Baroque. According to this research, the dominant note was repudiation and criticism, due to the gravitation of Catholic thought, especially after the scholastic revival of the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries. An author associated with the rupture between politics and Christian morality could only receive disapproval in that intellectual climate, although he has also been the object of tacit reappropriations, as has been pointed out regarding the figure of the “Christian prince” (Maravall, 1983; Fernández-Santamaría, 1986; Puigdomenech, 1988; Forte and López Álvarez, 2008; Howard, 2014; Bireley, 2018). About Spanish-American countries, and with a few exceptions, there is no significant body of research, and the available works (not necessarily in dialogue with the studies on the Spanish Baroque just cited), present a similar picture: disinterest, objections, scarce references.

A conclusion to be drawn from all this is that, unlike what was evidenced for the English-speaking space, Machiavelli would not have been an author of interest, and, secondly, that the reception of his work in a republican key (indicated by Pocock’s works, and also highlighted by classic studies on the United States—Baylin, 2012—) would have been of little visibility and prominence, since in the few references available, the prevailing topic would have been anti-Machiavellianism, that is, the conception of Machiavelli as synonymous with tyranny and immorality. As a result of all this, in 19th-century Latin American political thought, whether in times of independence revolutions or, a little later, of state construction, the Florentine would not have been a prominent name (Aguilar and Rojas, 2002).

This paper aims to contribute to this little-explored area of the circulation and reception of the author of *The Prince*. For this purpose, it will deal with a defined type of sources and record, the considerations left on the Florentine by Spanish and Argentinian professors of Political Law, in a period extending from 1914 to 1950 approximately.

This choice is based on two reasons. The first is that Political Law, an academic field that gained visibility and consistency at the turn of the 20th century, delineated a space of reflection that, due to its own characteristics, favored a reading and reception of Machiavelli with scholarly features, and not, therefore, exclusively or mainly motivated by political polemics; in any case, the approval or repudiation had to be deployed based on philosophical and doctrinal arguments that lent those positions intellectual, not solely political, foundations. The second reason is that, as a result of the ideological changes that occurred during the chosen period, it is possible to distinguish what arguments liberal and illiberal authors employed when reading and interpreting Machiavelli. From this point of view, the considerations made about the Florentine allow us to detect keys and features of the liberal and anti-liberal thought of the period. Moreover, since the corpus to be analyzed comes from the same field of knowledge, the exploration that will be carried out in the following pages offers the possibility of identifying shared references,

borrowings and discussions, as well as the circulation of knowledge, between Argentine and Spanish legal scholars.

LIBERAL READING: ADOLFO POSADA AND MARIANO DE VEDIA Y MITRE

Adolfo Posada (1860-1944) was one of the most prominent jurists in Spain between the end of the 19th and the first half of the 20th century. His biographical and intellectual trajectory highlights, on the one hand, his links to Krausism, an intellectual movement of great impact in Spain in the second half of the 19th century, due to the impulse it gave to social and reformist liberalism, as well as to the renewal of academic and intellectual life, which provoked confrontations with the Catholic Church, and even the separation of Krausist referents from the university system (as a result, they created the *Institución Libre de Enseñanza* in 1876, which lasted until the end of the Spanish Civil War in 1939) (Suárez Cortina 2000 and 2019).

On the other hand, Posada was an unavoidable figure of Spanish Political Law and of university life, through work in which topics such as the relationship between morality and law, the nature and characteristics of the State, legal pluralism, and the theory of self-limitation of state sovereignty (according to which the State self-limited its sovereignty to establish a legal regime, thus assuming the character of the Rule of Law, compatible, in turn, with “the legal recognition of personalities—individual and collective—within the State”—Posada, 1923, pp. 341-342) stand out.

At the same time, about his political positions, Posada was referenced with the aforementioned liberalism of reformist orientation of Krausist inspiration. It is worth noting the correspondence of these interests and perspectives with the Spanish political context of the turn of the 19th century, marked by the affirmation of a State based on liberal principles, within the framework of the so-called Bourbon Restoration (1875-1931). Later, Posada intervened in the design of the Constitution of the Second Spanish Republic approved in 1931. Finally, it is important to point out that he was an important and well-known figure in Argentina; he visited Buenos Aires on several occasions during the 1910s and 1920s, a city where some of his works were published.¹

Posada's focus on Machiavelli was enduring and concentrated on two main topics: the ontology and knowledge about politics that the Florentine had bequeathed, and the conception of the State that could be found in his writings. Regarding the first point, in Posada's opinion, the contributions Machiavelli had made to the knowledge of politics, and the very notion of what politics was, were worthless. His work was empiricist, devoid of ethical purposes, and therefore with authoritarian projections; an example of the “empiricism that makes of peoples true herds of slaves.” This same empiricist characteristic,

moreover, deprived it of scientific stature: “Machiavellian practice is the most complete expression of this politics of circumstance and anti-science. The man whose actions are inspired by those principles that the famous writer expounds in his *Prince*, has lost all notion of what is just” (Posada, 1884, pp. 248-249).

For Posada, on the other hand, the political projection of Machiavelli's realism had contemporary manifestations, no less than in the militaristic nationalism deployed during the “Age of Empire,” with Bismarck's Germany as the maximum example, which had culminated in World War I:

In spite of the time... of the emancipatory Revolutions, of the great democratic tide, of optimistic radicalism and of the advent of the consciences of the peoples to the scene of great political movements, we live in full mastery of the ideas and practices highlighted by the great Florentine, or rather, in full politics of *The Prince*, reinforced with new philosophical bases, and invigorated with the sap of broad sociological conceptions. Such politics has been re-made as a philosophy of history, and has become an art of success, for national aggrandizement and international domination. Machiavellianism has become Bismarckian; nationalism has made maximum use of the political substance—full of life and passion—of the famous Florentine's book. And now this refined substance nourishes imperialist internationalism (Posada, 1915, p. 11).²

In fact, for Posada, at least German militaristic nationalism had more visible ethical aims than those that could be seen in the Florentine's texts. Contemporary Machiavellianism, to some extent, was not a mere reversion of the original, which continued to condense opprobrious principles and values:

Undoubtedly, in the political philosophy of the aggressive, imperialist State, outwardly, and absolutist or domination—ruling—within, there is more than the pure Machiavellianism of *The Prince*. Even in the manifestations that can be considered more characteristic and of very direct influence on the development of the catastrophic process of the power-state, one can see, at times, the purpose of rectifying the very conception of Machiavelli own conception into something essential [...] Those who now affirm the omnipotence of the State and place the construction of a strong and domineering one above all else do not want to dispense with ethics. His point of view undoubtedly entails a broader and more mature conception of politics, and of more complex historical roots than that of *The Prince*; it has other perspectives and another vision of universal history. In its background—in Treitschke especially—is a desire or longing for moral greatness (Posada, 1915, p. 13).

It must be said that Posada's considerations were far from original. On the contrary, the Spanish jurist offered a singular version of a widespread conception of Machiavelli at the turn of the 20th century, according to which

¹ Posada, 1922. About Spanish Political Law, see Martín, 2011.

² See a similar argument, among others, in Rodríguez Aniceto, 1919.

the Florentine was an unavoidable reference for thinking about European politics at that time, precisely because his ideas and principles could be embodied in imperialist competition, the arms race and an expansionist and aggressive nationalism (Losada, 2023).

Beyond the latter, it is worth retaining two points from Posada's considerations. On the one hand, he had a clearly negative judgment of Machiavelli; but this was not based on understanding the Florentine as an author of tyranny or any other form of arbitrary personal government; instead, Posada's objections to Machiavelli lay, first, in his political ontology, and secondly, as a projection of this, in the type of State that his thought allowed him to found, a State that did not coincide with a State of liberal law, but with a State that promoted militaristic nationalism, responsible for nothing less than the First World War. The second point to highlight lies in the prisms that underpinned Posada's consideration, a conception according to which politics and morality could not be separated, derived from his Krausist positions.³

Mariano de Vedia y Mitre was the first Professor of Political Law at the University of Buenos Aires, a position he held between 1924 and 1946. From that chair, Vedia was the first professor to teach Machiavelli systematically in the Argentine university, and the promoter of the first book published in the country devoted entirely to the study of the Florentine's work (Vedia y Mitre, 1927). That was the first occasion on which Vedia expressed his considerations on the Florentine, which continued (without interpretative changes) throughout a series of works he published during the years 1930 and 1940 (Vedia y Mitre, 1926, 1934, 1952).

Vedia very much coincided with Posada vis-à-vis the themes that, in his opinion, were the backbone of the work of the author of *The Prince*. Similarly, to the Spanish jurist, for Vedia, these themes were the separation between morality and politics, and the State. The point to note is that this coincidence overlapped with diametrically opposed readings of the ideas and approaches that Machiavelli had made in this regard. For Vedia, Machiavelli was not synonymous with the validation of immorality in politics, and was a precursor of the modern notion of the State, the latter understood to be a rule of law, directed towards the security and freedom of its members.

According to the professor at the University of Buenos Aires, the Florentine had been a groundbreaking thinker and the founder of modern political science (which in turn provided knowledge for the "art of government") as a result of "his absolutely original conception that politics is a science independent of morality, which does not respond to preconceptions or established rules" (Vedia y Mitre, 1927, pp. XX-XXI). As for Posada, the foundational gesture to postulate this separation had been his realism: "the absolute separation between politics and morality did not appear as a hypothesis or an abstraction, because it was on the contrary a real fact" (Vedia y Mitre, 1927, p. XX-

III). Therefore, he emphasized that: "His thought is the antithesis of that of St. Thomas" (Vedia y Mitre, 1934, T. I, p. 279).

However, all this did not mean that Machiavelli was proclaiming that immorality was politically justified. The Florentine had certainly warned that sometimes one had to learn to be bad, but this did not involve ceasing to be good. He had separated politics and morality, but "nowhere does he praise immorality" (Vedia y Mitre, 1934, T. I, p. 280).

In line with this reading, for Vedia, the objectives or purposes that ran through Machiavelli's work were moral, not only political (an observation that, by the way, enabled a questioning of the autonomy of politics from morality). According to Vedia, the morally reprehensible actions mentioned by Machiavelli were only acceptable when the end pursued was beneficial to the majority: "for Machiavelli the wickedness of the sovereign, or his bad faith, is only justified when a higher good for the majority of the people is in view" (Vedia y Mitre, 1934, T. I, p. 277).

What was this "higher good"? To create laws and, through them, to introduce the notions of good and evil, unknown among men as a result of their constitutive amorality. Machiavelli's negative anthropology (which emphasized amorality rather than immorality) did not support arbitrariness or force. And the figure of the prince was that of the great legislator:

For him [Machiavelli] men are neither good nor bad; they are simply amoral. This does not mean that for him men cannot be good, but that for this to happen it is necessary for them to acquire the conscience that they do not have originally; that conscience of justice, that is, the difference between good and evil [...]. This is only acquired as a consequence of political coexistence, as Machiavelli wrote in the "Discourses." And to say that is to say the State, civil living, under the rule of law, for it is from them, from their application and their knowledge that moral conscience will be born. From this it follows, even if Machiavelli did not [...] say so, that the State achieves a moral end (Vedia y Mitre, 1946, T. V, pp. 387-388).

As can be read in this quote, then, Vedia (while recognizing a certain forced reading of the Florentine), understood Machiavelli as a theoretician of the State, since the figure of the prince evoked the creator of institutionality, and not the ruler clinging to personal power, whose sense was to establish the moral coordinates of society. This conception of Machiavelli is linked to a theoretical perspective enduring in Vedia, the theory of state self-limitation of sovereignty. According to this legal theory, critical of the theories of sovereignty that deposited it in a human agent (the king in its absolutist variant, the people in its democratic variant), as well as of classical liberal constitutionalism that postulated individual rights on which sovereignty could not intervene, sovereignty was in the State and it was the state self-limitation of that sovereign power that established the rule of law through positive legislation (Fioravanti, 2009).

³ One of Posada's intellectual references, Francisco Giner de los Ríos (1921, p. 186) left similar considerations about Machiavelli.

This state theory was very important in continental European political law in the second half of the 19th century, especially in those countries that had recently undergone the process of state building, Italy and Germany. And, it should be stressed, among its principal exponents, the conception of Machiavelli as the founding author of the modern state was widespread. In fact, in Italy this reading (in polemic contrast with that which conceived the Florentine as synonymous with tyranny) had been important in Romanticism and later during the Risorgimento, while in Germany it dated back to Fichte and Hegel. All these theoretical references are present in Vedia y Mitre and, therefore, his considerations on Machiavelli can be attributed to them (without ignoring the fact that they could also derive from direct readings of his writings). The Argentine jurist, in fact, understood *The Prince* as it had been read in these reading traditions, a text whose key chapter was not those most referred to in order to account for its perversities (the XVII or XVIII), but the last one, in which a call was made to rid Italy of the barbarians through an exceptional leader who would undertake the work of politically uniting the peninsula through the construction of a State that would enshrine self-determination.

The interesting point to note here is that, in line with the gravitation of the German theory of the State, emphasis has been placed on importance of Krausism in the legal formation of Vedia y Mitre, whose presence was important in Argentine politics and ideas at the end of the 19th century, and which was one of the reasons behind Adolfo Posada's work and visits to Argentina. The attribution of moral purposes to Machiavellian politics, and specifically to state action, can be conceived as a mark of this Krausist influence.⁴

The element to highlight, then, is that two jurists referenced with Krausism, Posada and Vedia, also located in the liberal camp of their respective countries, bequeathed opposite readings on Machiavelli. A referent of authoritarianism, immorality and a form of State at odds with liberal principles (State-power), in one case (Posada), the intellectual father of the modern State and of a policy with moral purposes, among which internal and external freedom stood out (Vedia y Mitre). In other words, similar political and doctrinal positions could lead to different and even opposite interpretations (and assessments). With its particular tones, a similar picture emerges when dealing with anti-liberal authors.

ANTILIBERAL READING. LUIS LEGAZ Y LACAMBRA, TOMÁS CASARES, FAUSTINO LEGÓN AND FRANCISCO JAVIER CONDE

Luis Legaz y Lacambra (1906-1980), was another renowned Spanish jurist of the 20th century, with an outstanding academic career. Professor of Philosophy of Law, he served as Rector of the University of Santiago de Compostela and Dean of the Faculty of Law at the

University of Madrid. Unlike Posada, he had anti-liberal sympathies and positions, certainly heterogeneous and even changing throughout his life. He has been labeled a fascist, Catholic, national unionist, and was a member of Falange, the political space on which Francisco Franco's regime was based. In turn, in his legal thought, his interest in the work of Hans Kelsen and Carl Schmitt, and the gravitation of natural law and Thomism have been highlighted (López García, 1996, pp. 127-171; García Manrique, 1996, pp. 179-185, 223-236; Rodríguez, 1997, pp. 85-141, 203-240; Rivaya, 1998, 2010; Sesma Landrín, 2013).

Legaz y Lacambra's interest in Machiavelli focused on a topic that also attracted Posada and Vedia, as was seen in the previous section, namely, ontology, the notion of politics that the Florentine had proposed. According to Legaz, the affirmation of the autonomy of politics had two possible meanings, to cut out a dimension of human life, or to identify a specific form of knowledge:

Two completely different issues are involved in this problem of politics; one, the recognition of politics as a science or art with its own formal object and subject, therefore, its own rules that cannot be reduced to theological or moral precepts without further ado; and the other, the recognition of politics as a normative ordering of human conduct, irreducible to the other normative orderings, moral and juridical, that is, the assumption that certain human actions would be neither moral nor juridical, but "political" and justified insofar as they are in accordance with this specific normativity, autonomous and irreducible to the others (Legaz y Lacambra, 1943, p. 243).

For Legaz, the first option was not objectionable, because it was based on political science as a field of knowledge. On the other hand, it was to conceive of politics as an autonomous and self-sufficient dimension, because "we cannot elevate the political to an autonomous value, of the same rank as the value of morality, nor can we believe, therefore, that there exists a system of norms ordering human conduct called 'politics', coordinated with the system of legal norms and moral norms." It was essential to oppose "all 'sanctification' of politics, a spiritual attitude that has its roots in the overvaluation of action for action's sake" (Legaz y Lacambra, 1943, p. 245). In short, "politics must be subordinated to morality" (Legaz y Lacambra, 1943, p. 252).

This type of objection, as can be seen, is similar to the considerations Posada left in his writings (we will return to this subject below). For the moment, it is important to point out that they were accompanied by another type of affirmation, regarding another crucial issue, the relationship between politics and morality. As a result of the split that Machiavelli had established between the two, Legaz y Lacambra argued that the Florentine bequeathed a notion of politics as "technique." This did not mean, however, that it was an immoral or even amoral politics. For Legaz, politics, as a technique, had an ethic, its own notion of good (which Legaz, of course, did not share): "Morality, as Machiavelli

⁴ About Krausism in Vedia y Mitre, see Arlotti, 2014. More generally, see Roig, 1969; Dotti, 1992, pp. 72-94.

conceives it, is, then, the ability to achieve good at all costs, understood as one's own utility and that of others. And this is exactly what politics is [...] Thus, every moral action is a technical action, even if not every technical action is moral" (Legaz y Lacambra, 1943, pp. 248-249).

Tomás Casares and Faustino Legón were exponents of the Catholic reactivation, in a neo-Thomist key, that took place in Argentina between the wars (a phenomenon that, of course, was far from being local and that Legaz y Lacambra himself also shows in his own way for Spain). Casares (1895-1976) was a professor at the Universities of La Plata and Buenos Aires, director of the Courses of Catholic Culture (a decisive space in the implantation of Thomism in Argentina) and President of the Supreme Court of Justice of the Nation between 1947 and 1949. For his part, Legón (1897-1959) was one of the founders of the aforementioned Courses of Catholic Culture, first full professor of Political Law at the National University of La Plata in the 1920s (he also held that chair at the University of Buenos Aires), first Dean of the Faculty of Law and Political Sciences of the Argentine Catholic University, and member of the Board of Directors of another Catholic house of higher studies, the Universidad del Salvador, in the 1950s (Dotti, 2000, pp. 171-184; Segovia, 2012; Arlotti, 2015).

According to Legón, Machiavelli was a minor figure in political thought and political science, since he had bequeathed a notion of politics that could only be defined as art. This characterization referred, once again, to how the effects derived from the separation between morality and politics were understood. Politics as art did not indicate a sophisticated knowledge or dimension of human life (as other authors understood it, from which an elitist conception of politics was derived—for example, Sánchez Sorondo, 1941—); it involved, instead (and in terms that, once again, recall those of Posada) a crude empiricism, a “trade oriented towards success and aggrandizement” (Legón, 1959, T. I, p. 60). Politics as an art was technical, and thus a degradation:

It is not to exhaust the true scope of political art, to consider it a mere empirical technique, with which the ruler ‘gets by’ with public business [...] the deeper meaning of political art [is]: skillful execution of certain objectives according to plans illuminated by intellectual and moral principles (Legón, 1959, T. I, p. 64).

For Legón, Machiavelli's teachings were based on a “false realism.” That is, in a distinction between politics and morality that was untenable, since there was no possible politics without an ethical dimension.⁵

In this direction, a politics stripped of ethical ends, and moreover immanent, that is, exclusively human, led to an adoration of the State (“statolatry”) that led to totalitari-

⁵ In some passages, Legón moderates the sharp separation attributed to Machiavelli between politics and morality by evoking his considerations on the relationship between good laws and good morals. The object of his attack, often, seems to be more “Machiavellianism” than Machiavelli himself: Legón, 1959, T. I, pp. 71-72; t. II, p. 323, footnote.

anism: “The set of thoughts that lead to conceive of the State or the political organ free of ethical constraints, naturally lead to what has been called ‘statolatry’, that is, an overvaluation of the State as an end in itself. Hegel, and earlier, Machiavelli [sic], concur in this” (Legón, 1959, T. I, p. 75, 510-513). In his perspective, the “Machiavelian slopes” ended in “tyranny without claim” inasmuch as they were intrinsic to a vision of politics in which “the first absolute is suppressed or forgotten, [and] one stops at secondary political absolutisms, intolerable, for not because they are secondhand absolutes, do they cease to be overbearing” (Legón, 1951, pp. 73-74).

Tomas Casares adopted a similar stance. Machiavelli, by separating politics and Christian morality, had given rise to modern relativism. Casares' singular emphasis was that the main consequence of the relativism opened by Machiavelli had been the creation of the conditions necessary for the possibility of liberalism:

The ultimate purpose of the exaltation of the State is the liberation of the individual by removing him from his subjection to God and creating an order of subjection of which he himself is the omnipotent author [...] the affirmation of this absolute autonomy creates in the political order the permanent danger—a danger that is at the very core of the system—of a new subjection infinitely worse because it would come from man himself and would be arbitrary, since the normative value of the transcendent law has been denied, which offers, in its transcendence, the guarantee of its unbreakability, its universality and its permanence (Casares, 1981, p. 65).

According to Casares, the postulation of an omnipotent State, in the sense of being freed from the limits provided by classical natural law or by the ultimate subordination to the transcendent authority of God, did not make Machiavelli an author of tyranny or an enemy of freedom. On the contrary, he was the unavoidable figure to turn to in order to understand the emergence of the substantive principles of liberalism (as well as its inconsistencies and aporias). Machiavelli had “frequently invoked liberty as a political ideal.” And that freedom was the “freedom of the State,” but also “individual freedom” (Casares, 1981, p. 62).

In other words, the affirmation of the radical autonomy of politics and the state had been a necessary condition for conceiving freedom as modernity had understood it. That is to say, a freedom that is individual and exclusively of this world, dissociated from duty, purely concrete and sensible, alien to any notion of moral perfection and transcendent projection:

We are faced with an individual end as in the case of the scholastic response, but with a very serious difference: in the latter the individual end is condensed into a *duty*, an absolute duty that transcends time, space and all contingent circumstances; in Machiavelli's position, which on this point sharply expresses the Renaissance vision of life, the end is expressed in a *right*, the individual right to realize life with the maximum of concrete happiness (Casares, 1981, p. 61).

Therefore, the problem was not, for Casares, “Machiavellian immorality,” but the disengagement that encouraged the amorality derived from the separation between politics and morality: “The starting point is a total and fundamental independence of man with respect to everything that is not himself” (Casares, 1981, p. 61).⁶ This implied that:

Life has value in itself, it is itself an absolute value; to live with the freest fullness as long as the freedom of others is not violated, such is the destiny of man; and if the State is to cooperate in any way with that destiny, it will be by offering its subjects an environment conducive to that full expansion (Casares, 1981, p. 61).

The aporia that had been unleashed since Machiavelli, constitutive of modernity, consisted in the fact that there was a “violent and inevitable opposition between state omnipotence and individual exaltation promoted by the example of the State and its disregard for the discipline of moral conduct. It is the intrinsic weakness of all greatness that wants to be against God” (Casares, 1981, pp. 62-63).

The “sanctification of politics” about which Legaz y Lacambra warned, a product of the postulation of its immanent and human nature, culminated in totalitarianism. However, it is worth noting, not for proposing principles and doctrines alien to liberalism, but for being the inevitable consequence of the irresolvable contradictions of modern and liberal politics.

A last author of the anti-liberal arc worth mentioning is Francisco Javier Conde (1908-1974), who, among other things, was Director of the main academic institution of Franco’s Spain, the Institute of Political Studies.⁷ According to Conde, Machiavelli had postulated a “positive, technical and pragmatic” knowledge:

Machiavellian knowledge does not pursue a transcendent goal, nor is it ultimately sanctioned by the idea of a Providence that governs human affairs and business; wisdom lies in understanding human movement, predicting the course of political events and then managing them as perfectly as possible. This is why the “wise” prince is not subject to faith or to the word given and must dispense with both when the reasons that moved him to give them are lacking. The positive, technical and pragmatic character of Machiavellian knowledge neutralizes from the beginning the sphere of knowledge in the face of moral and religious values (Conde, 1948, p. 154).

As we read in this quote, the separation between politics and Christianity, according to Conde, had not implied immorality, but value neutrality: “The words good

and evil lose their autonomous and substantive moral content to become neutral terms of a mathematical function” (Conde, 1948, p. 171). Therefore, the Florentine’s knowledge was defined as “technical.” And, at the same time, this neutrality was related to another feature of his thought, “rationality.” Rationality and technique made Machiavelli a foundational theorist of the modern state:

The political order will be, then, a highly rational order, where everything is rationally foreseen and calculated. Through this passage of Machiavelli we witness the birth of the modern State as a form of ultra-rational political organization, with its tendency towards rational centralism as opposed to traditional and feudal law (Conde, 1948, p. 198).⁸

The other central axis of Machiavelli’s thought was order. According to Conde, true political life is “living in true quietude [...] Machiavelli’s problem [...] is precisely ‘stability’ [...] The primary task of political wisdom lies in ‘restraining’ the movement of human nature, which is as important as restraining human passions.” Therefore: “The *vivere quietamente* is founded, then, on coercion” (Conde, 1948, pp. 162-164). Hence, Machiavelli’s modern trait is “the essential link between the political order and the military order”; “What is specifically ‘modern’ is that Machiavelli introduces the military order into the very essence of politics, attributing to the State the monopoly of the military” (Conde, 1948, p. 201).

In Conde’s reading, then, Machiavelli seems a distant antecedent of Max Weber’s work, rather than that of Carl Schmitt, an author with whom, for example, Legaz y Lacambra associated him.⁹ The “wisdom” of the Florentine consisted in having proposed rationality and the monopoly of legitimate violence as attributes of the State, and in having noticed the importance of non-rational aspects in political leadership (Conde was interested in Machiavellian *virtue* and understood it in a way close to Weberian charisma).

In short, for Francisco Conde, Machiavelli had been an author of order and of the State. He had not been an author of tyranny, nor of emergency powers, but, through the convergence between military order and political order (a point that, it is worth insisting, defined the modern trait of the Florentine), he offered arguments to support an authoritarian, or in any case, disciplinary exercise of power. Machiavelli could be recovered without associating him with totalitarianism or fascism (a usual reading in Falangist intellectuals until the mid-1940s, such as Conde himself or Rafael Sánchez Mazas), a key point consid-

⁶ From this point of view, Machiavelli, for Casares, had had more rupturist implications than Kant, since the latter, by theorizing “brilliantly the autonomy of the ethical norm, will say that this autonomous moral law must be able to become a universal norm.”

⁷ Conde has been defined as an expression of a “Falangism with Ortegian roots” (in reference to the philosopher José Ortega y Gasset): Sesma Landrín, 2013, p. 275. See also López García, 1996, pp. 79-126.

⁸ Other authors, on the other hand, also detected Machiavelli’s “rationalism,” but repudiated it, linking it to immorality (not value neutrality) and individualism. For example, Mellado, 1891, pp. 135-136.

⁹ For Legaz y Lacambra, the ontology of the Florentine and the concept of “the political” of the German author shared an “absolute” conception of politics (Legaz y Lacambra, 1948, pp. 241-248). Something similar was also maintained by Luis Sánchez Agesta (1959, pp. 50-51). For the Argentine case, see Dotti, 2000, pp. 135-166.

ering the importance of dissociating the Spanish regime from these phenomena in the context of the second post-war period and the incipient Cold War (Gallego, 2014, pp. 814-817).¹⁰ Likewise, the reading of Conde deployed in this text can be related to visible and enduring concerns of his work, such as the search to link personal and charismatic leaderships with representation and rationality (Saz, 2012). In this direction, then, for Conde, the Florentine had given solid foundations to political authority by conferring it evaluative neutrality. The separation between Christian morality and politics had been a key distinction that had strengthened, not weakened, leadership.

The review of the considerations on Machiavelli of academics and jurists of anti-liberal positions yields at first sight a similar panorama to the one that returned the counterpoint between Posada and Vedia y Mitre: coincidences in the themes highlighted in the Florentine's work, and interpretative oppositions, from which different evaluations of his place in the history of political thought are in turn derived.

Beyond this initial observation, the approaches of Legaz, Casares or Legón can be placed in a tradition of reading that, as was noted at the beginning of this work, had deep roots in the Spanish-speaking world and was even considered predominant in the understanding of Machiavelli: criticism, censure and disapproval based on Catholic conceptions and prisms. Neo-Thomism and the revival of classical natural law in the interwar years would be, from the point of view of the reception of Machiavelli, one more milestone in a long history.

Even so, it is worth highlighting a singular emphasis of these criticisms, because they represent a nuance in the framework of the Catholic condemnations of Machiavelli. The anti-Christian, even diabolical character of the Florentine was not that he had promoted tyranny or a policy opposed to freedom. The anti-Christian character lay in the fact that he had been the intellectual father of modernity and liberalism. This was so because it was understood that liberalism was responsible for the totalitarianisms of the 20th century, insofar as they embodied the inexorable destiny of the purely human and relativistic politics opened with Modernity, consecrated by liberalism, and promoted by the author of *The Prince*. Totalitarianism was not the opposite of liberalism, but its inevitable consequence. Machiavelli's anti-Christian politics, in short, did not lie in having validated arbitrary power, but in having formulated a relative and false notion of freedom and politics (whose ultimate destiny, yes, was arbitrary power). Instead of a revival of the politics of the "ancients" (of Roman paganism), the condemnation of Machiavelli, from these Catholic arguments, lay in attributing to him a radical modernity.

The second point to note is that these were not the only arguments deployed from anti-liberalism. Conde, as we

¹⁰ In fact, in a text immediately before the one cited here, Conde's considerations on Machiavelli have a more visible critical tenor, basically by stressing that the "appearance of truth" was sufficient in Machiavelli to guarantee political order, but this led to the creation not of a "political community," but of "an appearance of community, a despotic community": Conde, 1974, pp. 142-143.

have seen, had a generally more favorable opinion—albeit with ambivalence and oscillations—of the Florentine. He agreed in attributing modernity to him, in giving him a decisive place for the separation between politics and Christian morality (and from this, in conceiving politics as technique), in having postulated central notions on which the modern state was based, but he disagreed on the political consequences of all this. For Conde, through these postulates, Machiavelli had allowed the foundation of a State oriented above all to the achievement and maintenance of order, and strengthened leadership, necessary to consolidate social discipline (without understanding all this, on the other hand, as fascism). It is worth noting, moreover, that some anti-liberal authors, such as Legaz y Lacambra, also formulated, within the general framework of a critical and condemnatory reception, some positive considerations about Machiavelli, especially about his importance in having made possible the emergence of a science, or at least of a specific field of knowledge, on politics.

CONCLUSIONS

Two main conclusions can be drawn from the exploration carried out in these pages, linked to the two issues raised at the beginning of the article: the characteristics of Hispano-American political thought during the first half of the 20th century, and how Machiavelli entered Argentine and Spanish university teaching.

Regarding the first point, an initial observation is that the different (and opposite) evaluation of the Florentine author cannot be related to ideological or doctrinal positions. Liberal and anti-liberal authors alike praised and repudiated him, obviously because they found in him contrasting principles and legacies. Think of Vedia y Mitre and Conde. Both had a praiseworthy reading of Machiavelli (more the Argentine than the Spaniard), but because they understood his writings in opposite ways: a foundational referent of the modern rule of law, and a key author for having built a political reflection that made order and the combination of political power and military power its substantive principles.

These positive and even laudatory readings deserve to be highlighted more than the critical and condemnatory ones, since both in the Spanish and Latin American liberal and anti-liberal tradition there was a deep history of disdain for or discomfort with Machiavelli. Posada is an example of this period of that nature in liberal thought, and Casares, Legón or Legaz y Lacambra of the criticism of Machiavelli in Catholic thought. In this last field, however, it is necessary to underline a point made above: the anti-Catholic character of Machiavelli was attributed to his responsibility for the emergence of liberalism and, in a broader sense, of modernity.

Machiavelli's modernity, it should be reiterated, was a reading shared by almost all the authors seen in these pages (although later there were differences over what were the features that defined his modernity-liberalism, a point of view shared by the liberal Vedia y Mitre and the Catholics Casares, Legón or Legaz y Lacambra; the "rational"

authoritarianism referred to by Conde). It is a point worth highlighting because, as has also been said, it had been usual for criticism of Machiavelli to be based on his consideration as an author who had revived principles and political forms typical of classical antiquity. This was the case in the readings that, from a Catholic perspective, had emphasized his paganism, as well as in the liberal ones that had deplored the revival of principles such as militarism and even notions of freedom that (in a conception that referred to the oppositions drawn by Benjamin Constant or Fustel de Coulanges between the freedom of the ancients and the freedom of the moderns) were based on principles, such as the common good, which could clash and even justify the subjugation of individual liberties.

The latter is present, albeit in a nuanced way, in Posada's reading, associating Machiavelli with political principles and passions (warlike and expansionist nationalism, imperialism, in a more global sense, an international policy conceived from war and conflict, not from peace and cooperation) whose presence at the beginning of the 20th century was pernicious for international stability, as demonstrated by the fact that they had led, no less, to the Great War of 1914. For Posada, it could be said, Machiavelli was contemporary, but not modern, which is why he was dangerous.

Regarding the second point, it has been seen that the prevailing way through which Machiavelli entered the Argentine and Spanish universities was Political Law, a framework in which he was considered, fundamentally, an author who integrated the Theory of the State. This aspect deserves to be highlighted for several reasons. On the one hand, it is important to point out that the reception of Machiavelli in Spain and Argentina in relation to Political Law is not a bias of the chosen cases; that is, the search for sources was restricted to this type of intellectuals and academics. On the contrary, the search for Spanish-speaking authors who had written about Machiavelli showed that those who had done so in a scholarly way and not only in a political polemic since the late 19th century coincided in having been jurists and, more specifically, professors of Political Law.

Political Law as a vehicle for the reception and university incorporation of Machiavelli can be explained for several reasons; among them, that it was a precursor field of university teaching for the systematic approach of perspectives and subjects that had hitherto been subordinated, such as the theory of the State and the history of political thought and ideas (its link with political science has also been highlighted).

However, beyond the reasons, the reading of Machiavelli from the perspective of Political Law encouraged (it can also be said that it is biased) a certain way of conceiving his texts, his ideas and their significance. And this way can be contrasted with those that have been detected in other intellectual and academic geographies. For all the authors studied in these pages (it has already been said but it is important to emphasize it now), Machiavelli was a theoretician of the State more than an author of the forms of government.

The authoritarianism of his ideas was associated with the type of State he had promoted—the Power State referred to by Posada—rather than with the type of leadership or political regime, or with his eventual weighting of tyranny and personal power; the same can be said of his place in the history of liberalism, for those who understood him in this way; and other topics that aroused interest and controversy, related precisely to ideas and forms of government, such as republicanism, received practically no attention from the authors discussed here (the exception is Mariano de Vedia y Mitre). The controversies about Machiavelli had to do with what type of State he had promoted, the liberal State or the Power-State.

Consequently, if the reception of Machiavelli in the field of Political Law is considered as how the Florentine author entered in a systematic and scholarly way in the intellectual reflection of the Spanish-speaking world (at least as the Argentine and Spanish cases allow us to see this), this context of reception allows us to understand a type of intellection of the Florentine's work that differs from that indicated, for example, for the English-speaking world, in which, starting with the studies of John Pocock, his gravitation as a reference author of the republican tradition was emphasized.

The importance of Machiavelli as a theoretician of the State in the Spanish-speaking world, in turn, is connected precisely with the intellectual references of the scholars of Political Law analyzed here, prominent among which were (among other sources) German intellectual and theoretical currents, such as Krausism, or the theory of the self-limitation of state sovereignty. The understanding of Machiavelli as the founding author of the modern state was a topic reiterated in German authors associated with that way of conceiving state sovereignty, whose genealogy dated back, at least, to Hegel (a reading that was also recurrent in Italian authors cited by the Spanish and Argentine scholars discussed here, such as Vittorio Emanuele Orlando). In turn, as will be recalled, Machiavelli's connection with the Force-State was linked to the state form that Germany had acquired since the unification led by Otto von Bismarck.

Finally, a feature visible in the authors analyzed here, and also related to a reception molded in the field of Law, was the attention given to their conception of politics. In this field, its foundational character in the affirmation of the autonomy of politics, which in turn implied understanding it as purely and exclusively human (because autonomy derived from the independence of Christian morality and subordination to a transcendent authority), was the legacy that caused most discomfort, discomfort shared by authors inscribed in ideological antipodes, since it crossed liberals like Posada and critics of liberalism such as Casares, Legón or Legaz y Lacambra. The latter, it is worth noting, delimited the acceptance of the autonomy of politics when it referred to a field of knowledge (political science), but not to a dimension of human life.

A final point of interest can be drawn from this. The discomfort with or objection to Machiavelli was ultimately due to attributing to him a notion of politics detached

from ethical purposes, whatever the desirable sources of those purposes might be (philosophy, religion, morality, natural law). Even an author such as Vedia y Mitre, who considered the proclamation of the autonomy of politics a merit and not a problem, attributed ethical purposes to Machiavelli's politics, because in his opinion, *The Prince* was a great legislator who established the notions of good and evil through positive legislation (therefore, if his conception of Machiavelli differed from that of Posada, he shared with the latter the conviction that politics should have ethical purposes, derived from a common referentiality to both, Krausism).

The difficulty of understanding politics as “a thing in itself,” autonomous, was, in this sense, a notorious mark of Machiavelli's reception in the Spanish and Argentine authors studied here, probably derived, then, from an approach to political reflection from juridical perspectives that, whether from secular (such as Krausism) or Catholic (classical natural law) perspectives, understood that politics, law and morality could not be dissociated (a reason that underlies their discussions not only with Machiavelli, but also with political decisionism or legal positivism—with which, by the way, it was usual to link the Florentine—). In sum, these modalities of reception of the author of *The Prince* led to a singular conclusion, the deep reason for the objections to Machiavelli, the recognition of the autonomy of politics, and, simultaneously, discomfort with it.

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REFERENCES

- Aguilar, J. A. and Rojas, R., coords. (2002) *El republicanismo en Hispanoamérica. Ensayos de historia intelectual y política*. México: Fondo de Cultura Económica.
- Arlotti, R. (2014) “Las primeras lecciones de Derecho Político en la Facultad de Derecho y Ciencias Sociales de la UBA.” In: T. Ortiz, coord., *Nuevos aportes a la historia de la Facultad de Derecho de la Universidad de Buenos Aires*. Buenos Aires: Facultad de Derecho, UBA, pp. 47-82.
- Arlotti, R. (2015) “Las primeras lecciones de Derecho Político del profesor titular Faustino J. Legón en la Facultad de Derecho y Ciencias Sociales de la UBA.” In: T. Ortiz, coord., *Facultad de Derecho y Ciencias Sociales. Enseñanzas de su historia*. Buenos Aires: Facultad de Derecho, UBA, pp. 125-149.
- Baylin, B. (2012) *Los orígenes ideológicos de la Revolución norteamericana*. Madrid: Tecnos.
- Berlin, I. (1992) *Contra la corriente. Ensayos sobre historia de las ideas*. México: Fondo de Cultura Económica.
- Bireley, R. (2018) *The Counter-Reformation Prince Anti-Machiavellianism or Catholic Statecraft in Early Modern Europe*. Chapel Hill: The University of North Carolina Press.
- Casares, T. (1981) “La política y la moral. A propósito de Maquiavelo (1927).” In: T. Casares, *Conocimiento, política y moral. Jerarquías espirituales*. Buenos Aires: Docencia, pp. 53-73.
- Conde, F. J. (1948) *El saber político de Maquiavelo*. Madrid: Instituto Nacional de Estudios Jurídicos, Ministerio de Justicia y Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas.
- Conde, F. J. (1974) *La sabiduría maquiavélica. Política y retórica (1947)*. In: F. J. Conde, *Escritos y fragmentos políticos, Vol. I*. Madrid: Instituto de Estudios Políticos, 1974, pp. 117-143.
- Dotti, J. (1992) *La letra gótica. Recepción de Kant en la Argentina, desde el Romanticismo hasta el treinta*. Buenos Aires: Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, UBA.
- Dotti, J. (2000) *Carl Schmitt en Argentina*. Rosario: Homo Sapiens.
- Fernández-Santamaría, J. A. (1986) *Razón de estado y política en el pensamiento español barroco (1595-1640)*. Madrid: Centro de Estudios Constitucionales.
- Fioravanti, M. (2009) *Los derechos fundamentales. Apuntes de historia de las constituciones*. Madrid: Trotta.
- Forte, J. M. and López Álvarez, P., coords. (2008) *Maquiavelismo y antimachiavelismo en la cultura española de los siglos XVI y XVII*. Madrid: Biblioteca Nueva.
- Gallego, F. (2014) *El evangelio fascista. La formación de la cultura política del franquismo (1930-1950)*. Barcelona: Crítica.
- García Manrique, R. (1996) *La filosofía de los derechos humanos durante el franquismo*. Madrid: Centro de Estudios Políticos y Constitucionales.
- Giner de los Ríos, F. (1921) *Estudios Jurídicos y políticos*. Madrid: Imprenta de Julio Cosano.
- Howard, K. D. (2014) *The Reception of Machiavelli in Early Modern Spain*. Woodbridge: Thamesis.
- Landi, S. (2022) *La mirada de Maquiavelo. Un ensayo desde la historia intelectual*. Buenos Aires: Eudeba.
- Legaz y Lacambra, L. (1943) *Introducción a la Ciencia del Derecho*. Barcelona: Bosch Casa Editorial.
- Legón, F. (1951) *Cuestiones de política y derecho*. Buenos Aires: Perrot.
- Legón, F. (1959) *Tratado de derecho político general*. Buenos Aires: Ediar.
- López García, J. A. (1996) *Estado y Derecho en el Franquismo. El nacionalsindicalismo: F. J. Conde y Luis Legaz Lacambra*. Madrid: Centro de Estudios Constitucionales.
- Losada, L. (2023) *Machiavelli in the Spanish-Speaking Atlantic World, 1880-1940. Liberal and Anti-Liberal Political Thought*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.
- Maravall, J. A. (1983) *Estudios de historia del pensamiento español*. Madrid: Ediciones Cultura Hispánica.
- Martín, S. (2011) “Estudio preliminar, edición y notas.” In: *El derecho político de la Segunda República*. Francisco Ayala, Eduardo L. Llorens, Nicolás Pérez Serrano. Getafe: Universidad Carlos III.
- Mellado, F. (1891) *Tratado elemental de Derecho Político*. Madrid: Manuel G. Hernández.
- Pocock, J. G. A. (1975) *The Machiavellian Moment: Florentine Political Thought and the Atlantic Republican Tradition*. New Jersey: Princeton University Press.
- Portinaro, P. P. (2021) *La apropiación de Maquiavelo. Una crítica de la Italian Theory*. Salamanca: Guillermo Escolar Editor.
- Posada, A. (1884) *Principios de Derecho Político*. Madrid: Imprenta de la Revista de Legislación.

- Posada, A. (1915) *La idea del Estado y la guerra europea*. Madrid: V. Suárez.
- Posada, A. (1922) *Teoría social y jurídica del Estado. El sindicalismo*. Buenos Aires: Librería de J. Menéndez.
- Posada, A. (1923) *Tratado de Derecho Político. Volume I*. Madrid: Librería General de Victoriano Suárez.
- Puigdomenech, H. (1988) *Maquiavelo en España: presencia de sus obras en los siglos XVI y XVII*. Madrid: Fundación Universitaria Española.
- Rivaya, B. (1998) *Filosofía del Derecho y primer franquismo (1937-1945)*. Madrid: Centro de Estudios Políticos y Constitucionales.
- Rivaya, B. (2010) *Una historia de la filosofía del derecho española del siglo XX*. Madrid: Biblioteca Jurídica Básica.
- Rodríguez Aniceto, N. (1919) *Maquiavelo y Nietzsche*. Madrid: s/ed.
- Rodríguez, J. P. (1997) *Filosofía Política de Luis Legaz y Lacambra*. Madrid: Marcial Pons.
- Roig, A. (1969) *Los krausistas argentinos*. Puebla: Cajica.
- Sánchez Agesta, L. (1959) *Lecciones de Derecho Político*. Granada: Librería Prieto.
- Sánchez Sorondo, M. (1941) *La clase dirigente y la crisis del régimen*. Buenos Aires: Adsum.
- Saz, I. (2012) "Franco, ¿caudillo fascista? Sobre las sucesivas y contradictorias concepciones falangistas del caudillaje franquista." *Historia y Política*, 27, pp. 27-50.
- Segovia, J. F. (2012) "Faustino Legón: del derecho natural al derecho constitucional." *Anales de la Fundación Francisco Elías de Tejada*, XVII, pp. 83-136.
- Sesma Landrín, N. (2013) "Sociología del Instituto de Estudios Políticos. Un "grupo de elite" intelectual al servicio del partido único y del Estado franquista." In: M. A. Ruiz Carnicer, coord., *Falange, las culturas políticas del fascismo en la España de Franco (1936-1975)*. Zaragoza: Institución Fernando el Católico, Vol. 1, pp. 253-288.
- Skinner, Q. (1984) *Maquiavelo*. Madrid: Alianza.
- Strauss, L. (1964) *Meditación sobre Maquiavelo*. Madrid: Instituto de Estudios Políticos.
- Suárez Cortina, M. (2000) "El republicanismo institucionista en la Restauración." *Ayer. Revista de Historia Contemporánea*, 39, 3, pp. 61-81.
- Suárez Cortina, M. (2019) *Los caballeros de la razón. Cultura institucionista y democracia parlamentaria en la España liberal*. Madrid: Genuève.
- Vedia y Mitre, M. de (1926) *Curso de Derecho Político*. Buenos Aires: s/ed.
- Vedia y Mitre, M. de, dir. (1927) *Maquiavelo*. Buenos Aires: Universidad de Buenos Aires.
- Vedia y Mitre, M. de (1934) *Curso de Derecho Político*. Buenos Aires: Biblioteca Jurídica.
- Vedia y Mitre, M. de (1946) *Historia general de las ideas políticas*. Buenos Aires: Kraft.
- Vedia y Mitre, M. de (1952) *Derecho Político General*. Buenos Aires: Kraft.
- Zuckert, C. H. (2019) "Review Essay: Machiavelli: Radical Democratic Political Theorist?" *The Review of Politics*, 81, pp. 499-510. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0034670519000275>